

Passenger Flow Prediction Method based on Hybrid Algorithm: Intelligent Transportation System

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ABSTRACT:

Forecasting passenger flow at metro transit stations is a useful method for optimizing the organization of passenger transportation and enhancing operational safety and transportation efficiency. Aiming at the problem that the traditional ARIMA model has poor performance in predicting passenger flow, a hybrid prediction method based on ARIMA-Kalman filtering is proposed. In this regard, ARIMA model training experimental samples are integrated with Kalman filter to create a prediction recursion equation, which is then utilized to estimate passenger flow. The simulation experiment results based on the inbound passenger flow data of Nanjing metro station show that compared with the single ARIMA model, the root mean square error of the prediction results of the proposed ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid algorithm is reduced by 257.106, and the mean absolute error decreased by 145.675, the mean absolute percentage error dropped by 5.655%, proving that the proposed hybrid algorithm has higher prediction accuracy. The experiment results based on the passenger flow data of Nanjing metro station show that compared to a single ARIMA model, the proposed ARIMA Kalman filtering hybrid algorithm reduces the root mean square error of the prediction results by 257.106, the average absolute error by 145.675, and the average absolute percentage error by 5.655%. It has been proven that the proposed hybrid algorithm has higher prediction accuracy.

Keywords: ARIMA model, Kalman filter, hybrid algorithm, passenger flow prediction.

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INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of metro transit construction has increasingly made it the main mode of travel for passengers in the new era. The combination of artificial intelligence [1], cloud computing [2], internet of things [3], and digital twin technologies [4-6] holds great potential for transforming intelligent transportation and passenger flow presentation. Passenger flow prediction at metro transit stations is an effective way to optimize station passenger transportation organization and improve operational safety and transportation efficiency. However, station passenger flow changes will be randomly affected by various factors such as weather, seasons, holidays, etc., and have certain randomness and nonlinear characteristics. Therefore, how to improve the accuracy of passenger flow prediction has important practical significance.

At present, research methods for traffic passenger flow prediction worldwide mainly include time series, gray model, neural network, etc. Chen et al., [7] established an ARIMA prediction model for urban rail transit inbound passenger flow. Fu et al., [8] built a hybrid deep learning model such as ARIMA model to predict the passenger flow on a daily basis. A novel graph optimization simultaneous localization and mapping technique is introduced in [9], which utilized YOLOv5 and Wi-Fi fingerprint sequence matching. The suggested method employs fusion deep learning techniques to improve the precision and resilience of closed-loop detection for robot navigation. Dong et al., [10] shaped the temporal-spatial network long short-term memory model to anticipate metro inbound/outbound passenger movement. The suggested model is compared to four prediction models, including baseline, ARIMA, SVR, and LSTM. Lv et al., [11] combined time series with the LSTM method to establish a combined model for high-speed rail passenger flow forecasting, and fine-tuned the parameters of the model. Compared with other models, this combined model has higher forecast accuracy.

Jiao et al., [12] combined historical prediction error to the measurement equation and creates an error correction coefficient-based Kalman filtering model. Xu et al., [13] used Kalman filtering to predict subway passenger flow. Since the above single model has certain errors in passenger flow prediction accuracy, some scholars have proposed hybrid algorithms for improvement. Liu et al., [14] used BP neural network and gray model to predict highway traffic flow. The prediction results showed that this method has high accuracy. Xiong et al., [15] used wavelet analysis to denoise the original passenger flow data, and then combined the time series with a neural network to predict passenger flow, thereby improving the accuracy of the model.

The mechanism of the ARIMA model is to predict future values after training a large amount of historical data. However, because the data itself is susceptible to the randomness of external factors, there will be errors in the data basis for prediction. Kalman filter is used for adaptive noise reduction characteristics and can achieve the purpose of improving prediction accuracy by iteratively training the original data. It can be found that integrating Kalman filter adaptive data correction and noise reduction performance in the traditional ARIMA prediction model can effectively reduce prediction errors. However, at present, the ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid prediction algorithm is mainly used in fields such as output and network load, and has less applications in urban rail transit passenger flow prediction. Based on this, the ARIMA-Kalman filtering hybrid algorithm is used to predict railway inbound passenger flow. Taking the actual inbound passenger flow data of Nanjing metro stations as a research sample, an ARIMA model is established through Python software, combined with adaptive Kalman filter is used to modify the model to obtain the optimal. The ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid prediction algorithm is used to achieve the purpose of improving the accuracy of inbound passenger flow prediction.

METHODOLOGY

ARIMA Model

Time series analysis uses curve fitting and parameter estimation methods to establish mathematical models based on time series data obtained from system observations [16]. The method builds the most parsimonious ARMA model from a generic class using model identification, parameter estimates, and diagnostic testing continuously (as shown in Figure 1). The idea of time series analysis method is mainly to use historical data to predict future data. In this study, the time series

analysis method will use the extrapolation mechanism to describe the changes in the time series based on its own change rules.

Figure 1. The Sustainable Approach to the ARIMA Model

Before using time series analysis, it is necessary to perform differential stationarities on the data, judge white noise, and then perform predictive analysis. The ARIMA model is also called the autoregressive integral moving average model. This model consists of two models, one is the p -order auto-regressive (AR) model, and its calculation method is as:

$$X_t \varphi_1 X_{t-1} + \varphi_2 X_{t-2} + \dots + \varphi_p X_{t-p} + \alpha_t, t \in Z \quad (1)$$

where, $\varphi_0, \varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_p (\varphi_p \neq 0)$ are real numbers; p is the autoregressive order; X_t is the zero-mean stationary sequence; and α_t is the random error term, which is white noise.

Kalman Filter Model

Kalman filtering is based on the known variance of the measurement equation, uses the minimum mean square error as the estimation criterion, and uses a formula to predict the next data based on the previous data and the corresponding covariance. According to the data with measurement noise, the state equation of the linear system is, observation data, system noise, etc. undergo a series of transformations to predict the dynamic system equations and obtain the optimal estimation algorithm. The Kalman filter model mainly includes state and pre-measure.

$$X_{k+1} = AX_k + W_k \quad (2)$$

$$Z_k = CX_k + V_k \quad (3)$$

here, X_{k+1} is the state value at time k ; Z_k is the system measurement value at time k ; A is the state transition matrix; W_k is white noise; C is the observation matrix; and V_k is the observation noise.

The Kalman filter model adjusts the Kalman filter equation according to the spatial state equation. The basic idea of Kalman filtering is to use the minimum mean square error as the optimal estimation criterion. There are two main steps in building a model: iteration and prediction.

The design method of Kalman filter is convenient and can be realized through computer programming. It is this convenience that makes Kalman filter widely used in prediction. In addition, its application relies on the recursive method and the adaptability of the model, and has no major connection with historical data.

Hybrid Prediction Model

Due to the influence of weather, date and other factors, the forecast results are still far from the ideal value. Kalman filtering uses the system state to make optimal estimates, predicts data based on the adaptability of its own model, and improves the accuracy of the results.

Therefore, a prediction method of ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid algorithm is proposed to predict inbound passenger flow. The ARIMA model is first constructed, and the hybrid algorithm is obtained based on the model parameters.

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

Experimental Data

The inbound passenger flow data of Nanjing metro station in 2019 is used to conduct an example verification of the method described above. Taking the inbound passenger flow data for the whole year of 2019 as a research sample, the passenger flow time series was established after preprocessing the data. The established passenger flow time series is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Time Series of Original Station Data

After smoothing the passenger flow data, determine the model type and order. By establishing an ARIMA prediction model and combining it with Kalman filtering to construct a state space equation, the Kalman filtering is used to predict passenger flow. On this basis, the data of the first 359 days of metro station in 2019 were applied to the established model, and the data of the next 7 days were predicted. The data of the first 351 days of the year were then applied to the model, and the data of the first 15 days of the prediction were used. The first 331 days of data are applied to the model, and the next 30 days of data are predicted; the three prediction situations are compared to test the goodness of the established model. The research relies on a large number of sample data, with sufficient data support and a certain degree of reliability.

Prediction Analysis

Using the root mean square error (RMSE), the mean absolute error (MAE) and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) as performance measurement indicators for passenger flow forecasting, they can reflect the actual. The difference in values can also reflect the reliability of the measurement. Therefore, these three judgment criteria are used to measure the goodness of the ARIMA model and

the ARIMA-Kalman hybrid algorithm. Compare the error between the predicted passenger flow data and the actual inbound passenger flow data. The single algorithm and the hybrid algorithm improve the accuracy of the predicted data. The evaluation criteria are as follows.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y - y_i)^2} \quad (4)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m |y_i - y| \quad (5)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \left| \frac{y_i - y}{y} \right| \quad (6)$$

here, m is the passenger flow forecast date; y is the actual passenger flow value; and y_i is the predicted passenger flow.

Perform a unit root test on the created time series. After analyzing the test results, it is found that the P test value is 1.650×10^{-9} is less than the significant value 0.05, indicating that the established time series is stationary. Therefore, in this study, the data was not differentially processed, that is, $d = 0$. In order to determine the model type, the first 30 autocorrelation coefficients and partial autocorrelation coefficients of the passenger flow time series were calculated, and the results are shown in Figures 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Autocorrelation Coefficient

Figure 4. Partial Autocorrelation Coefficient

It can be seen from Figures 3 and 4 that the first 30 autocorrelation diagrams and partial autocorrelation diagrams are all tailed. From this, it can be determined that the model is $ARIMA(p, d, q)$ and the built sequence is stationary.

It is difficult to determine the model order only from the autocorrelation diagram and partial autocorrelation diagram, so the AIC, BIC and HQIC criteria are used to determine the model order. The order determination results are shown in Table 1. When $p = 3$, $d = 0$, $q = 2$, the values of AIC, BIC and HQIC are all minimum values, and the model is determined to be $ARIMA(3, 0, 2)$. The passenger flow time series is trained, and the training results are shown in Figure 5.

Combine the established $ARIMA(3, 0, 2)$ model with Kalman filtering. By using the ARIMA-Kalman hybrid algorithm to predict passenger flow, a comparison of the predicted results between the ARIMA-Kalman model and the ARIMA model is shown in Figure 6.

Table 1. Model Ordering Results

ARIMA (p, d, q)	AIC value	BIC value	HQIC value
(3,0,2)	5461.15	5488.44	5471.99

Figure 5. ARIMA Model Training

Figure 6. Comparison Between ARIMA-Kalman Model and ARIMA Model

The comparison of the absolute errors predicted by the ARIMA model and the ARIMA-Kalman model is shown in Figure 7. By comparing Figure 7, it can be seen that the ARIMA model predicts a large amount of error and error value in the inbound passenger flow data, while the ARIMA-Kalman hybrid algorithm produces a small fluctuation in the inbound passenger flow prediction error, with a variation range of around 0-100. Compared with the ARIMA model, the error value of the ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid algorithm is smaller.

Figure 7. Comparison of Absolute Errors of the Two Models

Calculate the prediction result errors of the ARIMA model and the ARIMA-Kalman model, and the results are shown in Table 2.

The RMSE dropped from 425.582 of the ARIMA model to 168.476 of the ARIMA-Kalman model, a reduction of 257.106. The MAE dropped from 311.944 of the ARIMA model to 166.269 of the ARIMA-Kalman model, a reduction of 145.675. The MAE percentage dropped from 10.610% of the ARIMA model to 4.955% of the ARIMA-Kalman model, a decrease of 5.655%. From the table, the three error

values of the ARIMA-Kalman hybrid algorithm are all smaller than the ARIMA model, which proves that the prediction value obtained by the hybrid algorithm is more accurate.

Table 2. Error Analysis Results of the Two Models

Model	RMSE value	MAE value	MAPE value / %
ARIMA	425.582	311.944	10.610
ARIMA-Kalman	168.476	166.269	4.955

In order to test the soundness of the model, the data of 359 days before 2019 of metro station were selected to use the ARIMA (3, 0, 2) model to predict the inbound passenger flow value in the next 7 days. 351 days of metro station before 2019 were selected. 15 d data is used to use the ARIMA (3, 0, 2) model to predict the inbound passenger flow value in the next 15 days. Similarly, 336 d of data from station before 2019 is selected to use the ARIMA (3, 0, 2) model. The inbound passenger flow value in the next 30 days is predicted, and the prediction results. However, compared with the single ARIMA model, the predicted value of the ARIMA-Kalman filtering hybrid model is closer to the actual value and has better accuracy. Then compare the error values of the two models in predicting passenger flow in the next 7 days, 15 days and 30 days, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Error Values of Three Prediction Situations of Two Models

Prediction time	Model	Error		
		RMSE value	MAE value	MAPE value/%
Future 7 days	ARIMA	215.823	154.243	4.208
	ARIMA-Kalman	98.255	97.571	2.810
Future 15 days	ARIMA	253.124	160.071	4.262
	ARIMA-Kalman	97.889	97.267	2.810
Future 30 days	ARIMA	233.297	175.417	5.261
	ARIMA-Kalman	93.817	93.267	2.808

Table 3 shows the comparison of the two methods based on the evaluation criteria. RMSE, MAE and MAPE can well reflect the accuracy of the prediction value. It can be seen from Table 3 that the three error values of the ARIMA-Kalman filtering hybrid model in the three cases are smaller than the error values of the single ARIMA model. This proves that the hybrid model can improve the accuracy of prediction to a certain extent, and the prediction performance is higher than that of the single ARIMA model.

CONCLUSION

Accurate passenger flow prediction can effectively ensure operational safety and improve transportation efficiency. However, the passenger flow prediction process is affected by many factors, and it is sometimes difficult to obtain accurate prediction results. In order to improve the passenger flow prediction effect, the Kalman filtering noise reduction mechanism is introduced based on the ARIMA model, and an ARIMA-Kalman filtering hybrid algorithm is proposed. The model was verified through the inbound passenger flow data of Nanjing metro station in 2019. The example result analysis shows that compared with the single ARIMA model, the ARIMA-Kalman filter hybrid algorithm has better prediction performance and can be used for inbound passenger flow prediction.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. S.A. Nawaz, J. Li, U.A. Bhatti, M.U. Shoukat, R.M. Ahmad, "AI-based object detection latest trends in remote sensing, multimedia and agriculture applications," *Front. Plant. Sci.*, vol. 13, id. 1041514, 2022. DOI: [10.3389/fpls.2022.1041514](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2022.1041514)
2. Z. Zeeshan, U.A. Bhatti, W.H. Memon, S. Ali, S.A. Nawaz, M.M. Nizamani, et al, "@Feature-based multi-criteria recommendation system using a weighted approach with ranking correlation," *Intell. Data Anal.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 1013-1029, 2021. DOI: [10.3233/IDA-205388](https://doi.org/10.3233/IDA-205388)
3. A. Niaz, S. Khan, F. Niaz, M.U. Shoukat, I. Niaz, J. Yanbing, J. "Smart City IoT Application for Road Infrastructure Safety and Monitoring by Using Digital Twin," in 2022 Int. Conf. on IT and Indus. Techn. (ICIT), IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-6. DOI: [10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989141](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIT56493.2022.9989141)
4. M.U. Shoukat, S. Yu, S. Shi, Y. Li, J. Yu, "Evaluate the connected autonomous vehicles infrastructure using digital twin model based on cyber-physical combination of intelligent network," in 2021 5th CAA Int. Conf. on Vehic. Control and Intell. (CVCI), IEEE, 2021, pp. 1-6. DOI: [10.1109/CVCI54083.2021.9661190](https://doi.org/10.1109/CVCI54083.2021.9661190)
5. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, J. Zhang, Y. Cheng, M.U. Raza, A. Niaz, "Smart home for enhanced healthcare: exploring human machine interface oriented digital twin model," *Multimed. Tools and Appl.*, pp. 1-19, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-16875-9)
6. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, W. Liu, F. Hussain, S.A. Nawaz, A. Niaz, "Digital Twin-Driven Virtual Control Technology of Home-Use Robot: Human-Cyber-Physical System," in 2022 17th Int. Conf. on Emerg. Technol. (ICET), IEEE, 2022, pp. 240-246. DOI: [10.1109/ICET56601.2022.10004685](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICET56601.2022.10004685)
7. J. Chen, "Short-term Passenger Flow Prediction of Urban Rail Transit based on ARIMA Model," *Highlights Sci., Eng. Technol.*, vol. 78, pp. 77-83, 2023. DOI: [10.54097/2k79rb37](https://doi.org/10.54097/2k79rb37)
8. X. Fu, M. Wu, S. Ponnarasu, L. Zhang, "A Hybrid Deep Learning Approach for Real-Time Estimation of Passenger Traffic Flow in Urban Railway Systems," *Buildings*, vol. 13, no.6, id.1514, 2023. DOI: [10.3390/buildings13061514](https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13061514)
9. M.U. Shoukat, L. Yan, D. Deng, M. Imtiaz, M. Safdar, S.A. Nawaz, "Cognitive robotics: Deep learning approaches for trajectory and motion control in complex environment," *Adv. Eng. Inform.*, vol. 60, id. 102370, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.aei.2024.102370](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2024.102370)
10. N. Dong, T. Li, T. Liu, R. Tu, F. Lin, H. Liu, Y. Bo, "A method for short-term passenger flow prediction in urban rail transit based on deep learning," *Multimed. Tools Appl.*, pp. 1-23, 2023. DOI: [10.1007/s11042-023-14388-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11042-023-14388-z)
11. S. Lv, K. Wang, H. Yang, P. Wang, "An origin–destination passenger flow prediction system based on convolutional neural network and passenger source-based attention mechanism," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 238, id. 121989, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121989](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121989)
12. P. Jiao, R. Li, T. Sun, Z. Hou, A. Ibrahim, A. (2016). Three revised kalman filtering models for short-term rail transit passenger flow prediction," *Mathem. Prob. Eng.*, vol. 2016, id. 9717582. DOI: [10.1155/2016/9717582](https://doi.org/10.1155/2016/9717582)
13. X. Xu, K. Zhang, Z. Mi, X. Wang, "Short-term passenger flow prediction during station closures in subway systems," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 236, id. 121362, 2024. DOI: [10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121362](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.121362)
14. Y. Liu, C. Wu, J. Wen, X. Xiao, Z. Chen, "A grey convolutional neural network model for traffic flow prediction under traffic accidents," *Neurocomputing*, vol. 500, pp. 761-775, 2022. DOI: [10.1016/j.neucom.2022.05.072](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.05.072)
15. Z. Xiong, J. Zheng, D. Song, S. Zhong, Q. Huang, "Passenger flow prediction of urban rail transit based on deep learning methods," *Smart Cities*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 371-387, 2019. DOI: [10.3390/smartcities2030023](https://doi.org/10.3390/smartcities2030023)
16. T. Dimri, S. Ahmad, M. Sharif, "Time series analysis of climate variables using seasonal ARIMA approach," *J Earth Sys. Sci.*, vol. 129, pp. 1-16, 2020. DOI: [10.1007/s12040-020-01408-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12040-020-01408-x)

